

Fort of Golconda – The Historical Study in South Asia

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Abstract: To understand the Golconda Historical study, The Fort History of Golconda- a case study of Golconda Rulers. The present study has formulated three hypotheses: the historical background of the Golconda fort and political history, and the early foundations of the Golconda fort. The Art & architecture of the Golconda Fort and a particular focus on Hindu Islamic architecture. Golconda as a trade centre. And multi-Industries in this region, Golconda Social and political Aspects and economic conditions of Golconda in the region. Water irrigation system for Agricultural development, what happened ending period of Golconda, the tourist place of the great Golconda.

Keywords: Art & architecture, Golconda fort, Golconda Rulers, Golconda political and socio-economical history, Golconda Industries and Trends of economical-Impact.

1. Introduction of Golkonda

The fort of Golconda is one of the most beautiful monuments and is situated 11 km west of Hyderabad. The grand structure, which the Kakatiya rulers of Warangal constructed in the early twelfth century, has initially been just a mud fort. Later, it was converted into an excellent fort with ramparts and granite walls by the Qutub Shahi kings. It was seized from one dynasty to another and finally taken into the hands of the Qutub Shahi rulers. The Walls, bastions, and battlements reinforced the Golconda fort; outdoorings and the stonework of lions, peacocks, and gryphons exemplify the Kakatiya dynasty's influence. With an Eleven-kilometres perimeter, 15- to 18-foot-high walls, about 70 ramparts, and eight massive missives, the fort appears nothing short of amazing. The name 'Golconda' originated from "Golla '.

Gol and "Konda, "which means "shepherd's hill". The ten-kilometre radius from Golconda to outer Hyderabad was once a market city known for its trade of diamonds. Darya-e Nur's diamonds, meaning 'sea of light', measuring 185 carats and now in Iran, were mined here only. Other eminent precious stones, specifically Kohinoor jewel, Hope precious stone, and Regent precious stone, are accepted to have been uncovered here as it were. The stronghold was constructed in 1143 AD by the Kakatiya rulers and was subsequently seized by the Bahmani realm in 1364 AD.

After the collapse of the Bahmani Sultans, Golconda rose to prominence as the seat of the Qutub Shahi dynasty around 1507. Over 62 years, the first three Qutub shakings expanded the mud

fort into a massive granite fort extending around 5 km. It remained the Rajadhani of the Qutub Shahi and expanded the fort, whose 7 km outer wall enclosed the town. The Golconda state became a focal point for Shia Muslims in India. For instance, In the 17th century Bahmani clerics, sheikh Ja far bin Kamal al-din and sheikh Salih Al- Karjakin both immigrated to Golconda. The Qutub shahi sultanate lasted until its conquest by Mughal Emperor Aurangzeb in 1687. Nine months later, the fortress held out against Aurangzeb all, Ing to the Mughals through treachery. Kancharla gopanna, popularly known as Bhakta Rama Dasu, a devout Hindu who constructed the great god Batrachia temple without informing the kings at that time, tana shah, was kept in a jail located inside the fort. The famous important builder of Golconda was Ibrahim Quli Qutub shah wail, the 4th Qutb king. Ibrahim was following in the spirit of the ancestors. The Qutub Shahi kings were the great royal family of builders who had ruled the kingdom of Golkonda since 1512. Their first capital (Rajadhani), the fortress citadel of Golconda, was rebuilt for defence from invading Mughals from the north. Golconda consists of '4' distinct forts with a 10 km long outer wall with 87 semicircular bastions, 8th gateways, and four drawbridges, with several royal apartments & halls, temples, mosques, magazines, and stables, inside the least of these is the furthest nook into which we enter by the "Fateh Darwaja" (Victory doors, alleged after Aurangzeb's victorious military walked in through this entryway) studded with goliath iron spikes (to keep elephants and different creatures from battering them down) close to the south-eastern corner. At Fateh, Darwaja can be experienced a fantastic acoustic effect, characteristic of the engineering marvels at Golconda. A hand's clap at a certain place below the dome at the centre reverberates and can be heard clearly at the 'Bala Hisar' pavilion, the most point a kilometre away. It worked as a warning note to the great royals in case of an attack.

The graceful gardens and park of the fort may have lost their fragrance, for which they were known 400 years before, yet a walk in these former gardens and parks would be in your schedule when finding the past glories of Golconda fort. Bala Hissar Gate is the important entrance to the fort located on the eastern side. It has a pointed arch end bordered by rows of scrollwork. The spandrels have yales and decorated roundels. The place above the door has peacocks with ornate tails

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flanking an ornamental arched niche. The granite block lintel below has sculpted yales flanking a disc. The beautiful designs of peacocks and lions blend Hindu – Muslim architecture.

2. Aims and Objectives of the Study

This study aims to discuss the architectural grandeur of the fort of Golconda in a critical, compact and comprehensive manner. It will highlight,

- To advance the study of the historical background of the Golconda fort.
- To advance the study of the art and architecture of Golconda fort.
- To advance the study of trade in Golconda fort.

Scope of study:

The present study is concerned with analyzing the fort of Golconda's historical background and art & architecture and Golconda as a trade centre in the 15th century. It also deals with the social and cultural conditions under the Qutub Shahi dynasty.

Review of literature:

Marika Sardar's *A mirror of the evolving Deccan*, all rights researched, 2007. This book deals with the complete historical background of Golconda fort. In this book, we learn about the rich political history of the Golconda Qutub shahis.

Sharmila Durai's *The Amalgamation of Indo Islamic architecture of Deccan*. Department of Architecture, school of planning & architecture, Jawaharlal Nehru Architecture & fine arts university, India. This work helped the Golconda fort Architecture and a special focus on Indo- Islamic architecture.

J.D.B. Gribble's *A history of Deccan*, Landon: LUZAC & co-publishers to the Indian office 1896. This book deals with the Golconda fort History and trade under the Qutub shahis.

Outline of the sections:

The Introduction of the great Golconda fort.

The introduction of the Golconda fort and regional geographical landmarks in southern India.

List of political rules of regional forts and later Mughals rules in the southern part of India.

The Historical background:

This section will analyse the historical background of the Golconda fort. It pays special attention to the political history of Golconda Ruling Kingdoms.

The Art & Architecture:

The third section analyses the art and architecture of the Golconda Fort, with a special focus on Indo-Islamic Art.

The Golconda as a trade Centre under the Qutub shahis:

The fourth chapter focuses on the Golconda economy under the Qutub shahis.

The Water Irrigation System in the Golconda region:

The water source of Golconda: expressed about water management systems in Agriculture fields, how there is water supply to Golconda.

Conclusion:

The fifth section provides the general summary of the present research. Isn't only points out the limitations of the present work but also suggests future work.

3. Historical Background

The early foundations of Golconda fort:

Golconda was initially known as manual. Golconda stronghold was worked by the Kakatiya tradition as a component of their western protections as per the Kaanapali fortress. The city and the stronghold were based on a high rock slope, encompassed by huge bulwarks, 120 meters (480 ft). Rani Rudrama Devi and her replacement Pratap Rudra modified and reinforced the fortification. Afterwards, the post went under the control of the murumuru Nayaks, who crushed the Tughlaq armed force involving Warangal. It was surrendered by the murumuru papaya Naidu to the Bahmani sultanate as a feature of an arrangement in 1364. Under the Bahmani sultanate, Golconda gradually rose to conspicuousness. King Qulin-Qutb-ul-Mulk (1487-1543), sent as a legislative leader of Telangana, laid it out as the seat of his administration around 1501. Bahmani rule was continuously debilitated during this period, and King Quli officially became free in 1538, laying out the Qutb-shahi administration situated in Golconda. North of 62 years, the initial three Qutb-shahi kings extended the mud post into the current design, a huge fortress of rock reaching out around 5km in this situation. It remained the capital of the Qutb-shahi dynasty until 1590 when the capital was shifted to Hyderabad. The Qutb-shahis expanded the fort, whose 7km outer wall enclosed the city. The fort fell into ruins in 1687, after an eight-year siege leading to its fall at the hands of the Mughal Emperor Aurangzeb.

Golconda consists of three connected but separate fortified areas known as the Bala Hissar (lofty litadel). The outer fort, and the Naya Qila (new fort). Clustered within the walls of the Bala Hissar are several courtly buildings, while the outer fort contains mosques, shops, and residences. In the Naya Qila are two mosques and the remains of the garden and its pavilions, and just north of the fort is a group of domed tombs belonging to the Qutb-shahi family.

Golconda fort under the Kakatiya and musunuri dynasties:

The Kakatiya line constructed the Golconda stronghold to shield the western piece of their realm. The fortress is based on top of a stone slope. Rani Rudrama Devi and her replacement Pratap Rudra reinforced the stronghold further. After this, the musunuri line assumed control over the stronghold by overcoming the Tughlaq armed forces. Later the fortress was given to the leaders of Bahmani sultanate by Musunuri kapaya nayaka.circumstance

Rise of the Bahmani kingdom:

The Musunuris, a federation of local leaders based in Warangal, who had driven the Tughlaqs out of this portion of the Deccan, remained to rule the area around Golconda. Bahman Shah was able to subdue Bahman Shah to some extent. Many of these chiefs were forced to pay tribute to the Bahmanis, but he was never fully compensated. The Tughluqs once occupied the Telangana region, which the Tughluqs now control. He organized the forts he did have in 1357, including Bidar, Bhongir, Indore, and others. Azim moved the Kaulas into the province of 'Tilang,' and placed them under his supervision. Humayun is the illustrious son of a high-ranking courtier. Golconda, on the other hand, remained just outside.

out of the grasp of the Bahmanis. When Bahman Shah's successor Muhammad (r.1358-75) discovered that the Musunuris' leader had sought to ally with two of his greatest rivals, the kings of Delhi and Vijayanagara, Muhammad "decided on the full conquest of Telingana." He sent the governor, Azim Humayun, on a march to Golconda, with warriors from the Sultan's army accompanying him. The northern province, has marched on Warangal. Eventually, the Musunuri chief emerged victoriously was forced to file a peace suit. The fort, which constituted the Bahmani kingdom's eastern frontier, was given to Azim Humayun. For the next 150 years, Golconda was crucial in securing this border as control of the eastern shore moved from the Portuguese to the British. Musunuru to several other local dynasties, all of which have managed to survive. From the west, it is independent of Bahmani control. It appears logical that the fort would have changed over time (ca.1363-1495), especially given that references in contemporaneous histories show that it was a key place for organizing and deploying military forces. public relations campaigns (as will be discussed below). However, there is currently no scholarship on the subject. Even though, as is true for the period of the Bahmani, there is no discussion of the Bahmani period at Golconda, There is a great deal of physical evidence for this period of the site's history. The summit of the Bala Hisar has three features that appear to date from the mid-fourteenth to late-fifteenth century when the Bahmanis controlled the fort. (As shown on Plate 61's plan.) As well as revealing insight into an up until recently obscure part of history, These developments are like Bahmani-period relics of Golconda's development. different areas, suggesting that building processes at the various fortresses were comparative. This kingdom's ruler. The first of these elements is a gate near the northeastern corner of the Bala Hisar's second enclosure. It is made out of an inner post-and-lintel frame made of reddish-grey stone encased in a rubble exterior frame. The stone is encased in ornately sculpted plaster (Plates 62 to 64) The frame around the outside is made up of two parts: an outside rectangular section and an inner arched part.

The arched portion on the inside is divided into two planes and rests on two rectangular pillars that stand on a square base. The ledge that runs horizontally has animals and rosettes and stucco lotus bud moulding, spandrels. A tiny arched niche sits directly above the lintel. Previous scholarship on the site doesn't address this gate at all, and most works don't mention it. Sherwani was perhaps the first to bring this up. He describes the stucco animals as yalis (mythical leonine beasts also known as lionesses). swans with snakes in their beaks, lion cubs, peacocks, and parrots), vyalas or sardulas), swans with snakes in their beaks, lion cubs, peacocks, and parrots the presence of these symbols here and on a gate entering the palace area, he believes, is due to "the Kutb Shahi period's synthesised Indo-Muslim civilization." Michell also. gives a brief description of the gate and mentions the striking artwork; subsequent survey Books that include the gate directly copy his description. None of these authors has written a book. Speculates on the gate's age or tries to comprehend its symbolism.

Later, under Ala ud-Din Ahmad II (r.1436-58) and his

successor Humayun (r.1458-61), the Telangana region proved challenging to rule, as local leaders under the Bahmani's sought assistance from the monarch of Afghanistan. To fight their oppressors, Orissa (to the north) was formed. The governorship was given to Humayun. Off Telangana to an officer with the rank of commander and the title of Khwaja Jahan a thousand times, The Bahmani's flourished under Muhammad III's reign (1463-83). The Orissa army assaulted the Telangana provinces, forcing the Bahmani monarch to flee. They spent over three years in the region battling off this assault and putting an end to the insurgency. It had sparked uprisings. Golconda became more critical after the battle for Telangana was re-fought in the early to the mid-fifteenth century. It seems to have been underlying a similar way yet inside the bounds of the first fourteenth-century village. The excess Bahmani highlights were totally found in the second fenced area of the stronghold's internal fortresses.

Establishment of the Qutb Shahi kingdom:

The dynasty's founder, Sultan Qulin-Qutub-Ulf-Mulk, was a descendant of Qara Yusuf. He migrated to Delhi with his uncle, Allah-Qulin, some of his relatives and friends at Toward the start of the sixteenth hundred years in Hamdan area. Later he moved south to the Deccan and served the Bahmani ruler, Mohammad Shah. After the breaking down of the Bahmani Kingdom, he vanquished Golconda into the five Deccan sultanates. Before long, he declared autonomy from the Bahmani Sultanate, took the title Qutub Shah, and laid out the Qutb Shahi administration of Golconda. He was subsequently killed in 1543 by his child, Jamsheed, who expected the sultanate. Jamsheed kicked the bucket in 1550 from disease. Jamsheed's young child ruled for a year, when the honorability was brought back and introduced Ibrahim Qulin as king. During the rule of Muhammad Qulin Qutb Shah, relations among Hindus and Muslims were fortified, even to the reason behind Hindus continuing their strict celebrations like Diwali and Holi. A few Hindus rose to conspicuousness in the Qutb Shahi express, the main model being the clergymen's Madonna and Akkanna. With the development of the Char Minar, later Hyderabad, Golconda filled in as the sultanate's capital, and the Qutb Shahi kings adorned the two urban communities. The line controlled Golconda for a considerable length of time until the Mughal ruler Aurangzeb vanquished the Deccan in 1687.

The Qutb Shahi Kingdom was like the other Deccan realms, a profoundly concentrated state. The ruler appreciated outright leader, legal and military powers. Whenever practicality requested, the post of official was made to carry on the organization in the interest of the ruler. The Peshwa (Prime Minister) was the most elevated official of the sultanate. He was helped by a few pastors, including Mir Jumla (finance server), Kotwal (police chief), and Khaznadar (financier). In the Qutb Shahi realm, every one of the Muslims were paid recompenses from the depository. The Persian beginning Muslims had the most elevated regard and were paid the most elevated than the other Indian Muslims. The Persian origin Muslims became wealthy by lending money on high interest (usury) of 4-5% per mensem, much to the despair of Hindus. The Sultanate had 66 forts, and Nayak administered each fort. The Qutb Shahis hired

many Hindus Nayaks belonging mainly to the Kamma, Velama, Kapu, and Raju communities.

These gatherings essentially were the provincial nobility, filled in as income officials and military commandants, however a significant number of them fell into haziness following the fall of the Qutb Shahis in 1687. Charge assortment was through closeout cultivates; the most elevated bidder used to get the Governorship. While the Governors partook in a lavish way of life, they needed to endure the worst part of extreme disciplines for default. Subsequently, they were brutal on individuals. Individuals were in trouble as the protests of the poor never arrived at the rulers. The Qutb Shahi rulers belittled Turkish culture however in the end embraced the territorial culture of the Deccan, represented by the Telugu language and the recently evolved Deccan expression and Urdu became unmistakable.

Despite the fact that Telugu was not their native language, the Golconda rulers talked and composed Telugu and disparaged Telugu so only they were named the "Telugu Sultans". In 1543, dreading for his life, Prince Ibrahim Quli escaped to the Vijayanagar court, which sumptuously belittled the Telugu language. Upon his enthronement as king in 1550, Ibrahim Quli was entirely familiar with Telugu style. The Qutb Shahi rulers were incredible manufacturers whose designs incorporated the Char Minar and supporters of learning. Quli Qutb Mulk's court turned into an asylum for Persian culture and writing. Ruler Muhammad Quli Qutb Shah (1580-1612) composed sonnets in Dakhini Urdu, Persian and Telugu and left an impressive verse assortment. Nonetheless, ensuing artists and essayists wrote in Urdu while utilizing jargon from Persian, Hindi, and Telugu dialects. By 1535, the Qutb Shahis involved Telugu for their income and legal regions inside the sultanate. This line crossed 171 years throughout the entire existence of South India. The eight lords of this illustrious line have had a firm effect of areas of strength for them upon the land and its kin. The Qutub Shahi rulers were incredible manufacturers and supporters of learning. They belittled the Persian culture and the local culture of the Deccan, represented by the Telugu language and the recently evolved Deccan maxim.

Qutub Shah 1: SULTAN QULI QUTB UL MULK:

The organizer behind the Qutub Shahi realm did a lot to fortify and work on the capital Golconda. He embellished his fort capital with mosques, royal residences and nurseries. On the groundworks of the old mud fortification, Sultan Quli assembled an enormous bastion. This city called Muhammad Nagar before long multiplied and procured acclaim as one of the main urban areas of the east, notable for its exchange of jewels and valuable stones. Ruler Quill's subjects appreciated him, and he administered compassion and liberally. However, at 99 years old, the ruler kicked the bucket because of his child Jamsheed Quli.

Qutub Shah 2: JAMSHEED QULI QUTUB SHAH:

Jamsheed, the 3rd son, took over the reins of govt with blood-stained hands. His seven-year rule was set apart by individuals' hatred of his patricide. Be that as it may, Jamsheed Quli was taught and cherished verse. He passed on in 1550 of a hopeless infection.

Qutub Shah 3: SUBHAN QULI QUTUB SHAH:

He was 7 years old when he became Sultan of Golconda after his father's death, Jamsheed Quli Qutb Shah, in 1550 AD. Saif Khan, also known as "Ainul Mulk", was sent from Ahmednagar to perform the duties of the regent during the boy's development. Subhan died the same year, and his father's brother Ibrahim Quli Qutb Shah ascended the throne.

Qutub Shah 4: IBRAHIM QULI QUTUB SHAH:

The most youthful child of Sultan Quli Qutub Shah, Ibrahim, lived someplace far off, banished in shame as a respected visitor of the Raja of Vijayanagar. During this stay, he figured out how to cherish Telugu and talk it practically like his subsequent first language. when he ascended the throne, Ibrahim patronised and supported the learning and composing of Telugu as hardly any Muslim or non-Muslim rulers had done before him. Writers from everywhere the Deccan merged at Ibrahim's court. During his rule, Golconda was additionally fortified. Ibrahim Quli Qutub Shah welcomed his aristocrats to develop structures inside its dividers; mosques, Schools, Almshouses, and the Dam at Hussain Sagar, Budvel and Ibrahimpatnam were all shockingly. Additionally, Ibrahim was noted for his capable organization.

Qutub Shah 5: MUHAMMAD QULI QUTUB SHAH:

During the long, peaceful and prosperous reign of the fifth king Muhammad Quli Qutub Shah, the Qutub Shahi administration arrived at its peak. Muhammad Quli was delegated lord when just 15 years old. He is best recognized as the incredible organizer and pioneer behind the city of Hyderabad. As per well-known legend, the ruler was captivated by an artist considered Bhagmati, having a place with a little town of Chichelam where the popular Charminar currently stands. He tracked down Bhagnagar to propagate his affection for her, and the lord in like manner changed the name of the city to HYDERABAD. Muhammad Quli Qutub Shah, similar to Ibrahim, belittled and energized the Telugu language however much he did Arabic and Persian. He was a refined writer in Telugu and encouraged nearby practices and customs. He was likewise the maker of the main Deccani verse. Muhammad Quli was not really 48 when he passed on in 1612 after a genuinely lengthy rule of 32 years. Besides being a great builder and a man of letters, he was a humane and just king. Hayath Bakshi Begum was his only daughter married to his nephew and successor, Sultan Muhammad Qutub Shah.

Qutub Shah 6: SULTAN MUHAMMAD QUTB SHAH:

The nephew and child in-law of Muhammad Quli, Sultan Muhammad climbed the high position as the 6th Qutub Shah. A knowledgeable researcher, he had a profoundly strict personality and was an authority on good books. The Qutub Shahi accounts were finished during his rule. He further added to the building accomplishments of the Qutub Shahi tradition. The underpinning of the central mosque Mecca Masjid was laid during his reign in 1617. He likewise started the development of the structure of Sultan Nagar. These ventures were anyway not finished in the course of his life.

Qutub Shah 7: ABDULLAH QUTB SHAH:

Child of Sultan Muhammad, Abdullah climbed the high position at 12, his mom directing the realm till he accomplished

development. He carried on with an existence of delight and simplicity. However, the Kingdom was stretched out during his standard, it went under Mughal tension in 1636. Golconda was gone in 1656 and therefore, weighty repayment must be paid. He kicked the bucket on the first of May 1672.

Qutub Shah 8: ABUL HASAN TANA SHAH:

Abul Hasan, otherwise called Tana Shah, was Abdullah Qutub Shah's child in regulation. He demonstrated a capable ruler and a firm protector even with the Mughal may. He is recognized as a harmless and open-minded ruler who set his kin's thriving and prosperity above all the other things. Tana Shah was the last ruler of Golconda. During his standard, the Mughal Emperor Aurangzeb held onto the stronghold of Golconda for 8 constant months. In 1687, the Mughals at long last raged the stronghold after a trickster opened the doors. Abul Hasan was taken prisoner. He was held hostage first at Bidar and afterward at Daulat Abad (Aurangabad) where he kicked the bucket in jail following 12 years of bondage. Jan Sappar Khan, one of the aristocrats of Aurangzeb, went with Abul Hasan up to Daulat Abad. He was subsequently made the legislative leader of the Deccan under the Kingdom of Aurangzeb.

Mughal and Asaf Jahi rule of Golconda:

Golconda appears to have suffered surprisingly little damage given the length of the siege it endured in 1687. The fort was not plundered following its collapse, and Aurangzeb withdrew his camp to Hyderabad nearly immediately, leaving the fort alone. Almost no one is there. He stayed there while both Qutb Shahi cities' coffers were being raided, were inventoried, packed, and dispatched to Delhi; in the interim, he set up the infrastructure for the new province's administration, of which many people are a part. Former Qutb Shahi officers were retained and promoted to man Sardar in the army. The administration of the Mughals. Aurangzeb left the Deccan in January 1688. Jan Sippar Khan had been appointed governor of the province of Hyderabad and had relocated to Hyderabad, the provincial capital, by this time. Jamaluddin Khan, a qadar (fort commander), was posted to Golconda. Other Officers of the same rank were assigned to several Qutb Shahi forts, including Bhongir, Kaulas, Koilkonda, and Warangal, all places in Andhra Pradesh. There is little precise information on happenings at Golconda throughout the next quarter-century, even though it was a tiny fort in the grand scheme of the Mughal Empire (although it had a brief moment of fame when a son of Aurangzeb was killed there). In 1708, he declared himself "Emperor of Golconda." According to a poll of the region's residents.

However, history suggests that Golconda would have remained an important component of the empire's defences of the province. Mubariz Khan, an officer, was named governor of Hyderabad in 1713. His son, Khwaja Ahmad Khan, was named qadar of Golconda (the previous qiladar was believed to have been there until at least 1695). During their time in power, they were also confronted by Maratha. In 1718, Ahmad Khan was besieged at the fort, and the fort was besieged. It is difficult to discover information on Golconda in Asaf Jahi era chronicles. It is known that an officer called Himmat Khan was placed in

charge of the fort during the reign of the first Nizam; a 1739 instruction advises the fort's commander. Warangal district revenue collector to deposit money at a treasury at Golconda. This Nizam is also said to have encircled an unnamed hill with a wall to the east of the fort. Other facts can be found in a gazetteer commissioned by Nizam Mir Mahbub Ali Khan in the late nineteenth century.

The coronation of Muzaffar Jung took place in Golconda; Mir Nizam Ali Khan was crowned in Hyderabad. In 1802) and erected the Nau Mahal near the fort's congregational gate, opposite the palace area gate. mosque. Mubariz Oddala, Sikander Jah's brother, died a few years later. After being identified as a participant in a plot to overthrow the government, he was imprisoned by the British. The fort appears to have received little attention until the late nineteenth century when the first efforts to preserve its buildings as historical monuments were made. Salar Jung I, a minister who served three Nizams between 1853 and 1883, the tombs were walled in and a new garden was erected around them.

Mir Osman Ali Khan, the tenth Nizam, established an archaeological department in 1914 to support the work of the Indian Archaeological Survey. The tombs appear to have been preserved at this period, although the fort buildings were not: Some of the Nizam's men were armed, according to Bilgrami, who wrote in the early 1920s. The fort is where they are stationed. The Archeological Survey of India assumed control over the stronghold's conservation soon after the free territory of Hyderabad was assimilated into the new Indian republic in 1948. While the royal grounds have now been cleared and made tourist-friendly, The Indian Army continues to occupy the southwest quadrant of the country for research objectives. residences in the rest of the outer fort and the plains around the Mecca Darwaza the Qutb Shahi mosques and bazaars are still in use, and the Qutb Shahi mosques are still in operation.

4. Art and Architecture of Golconda Fort

Golconda Fort:

The original name of the Golconda fort is Mankal, according to the "Maathire-Alamgiri." The Kakatiyas of Warangal built the fort in the 13th century. The walls were erected with mud by Deo Rai, Rajah of Warangal's predecessors. Local chieftain Kishan Rao built the initial fort out of mud and brick in the 13th century. The Qutb Shahi Sultans renovated the Golconda Fort, which served as the Qutb Shahis' capital for a time. It was a 9-kilometre drive west of Hyderabad. Sultan Quli, the fort's first monarch, is said to have built the fort border wall of the fort. He has also constructed the Safa Mosque in the fort for the Sultan, the royal family, and his ministers to pray. An inscription carved on the Mosque's gateway explains Sultan Quli's role in the Mosque's construction. Abdul Karim hand wrote the inscription. In the fort, Sultan Quli built the Royal Palace "Dawlatkhana." Golconda has been called Muhammadnagar by him. Ibrahim Qutb Shah improved the fortifications and expanded the territory.

On the instruction of his Peshwa Mustafa Khan, he fortified the defensive walls by constructing a splendid wall of more than 7000 running metres. The Mecca Darwaza on the wall's south-

western part, which faces Mecca, was built in 1559-60. The fort was built during 62 years beginning in 1518 A.D. The fort's elevation is roughly 400 feet, and its perimeter is 4 miles long, with 87 semicircular bastions ranging in height from 50 to 60 feet. Sultan Abdullah Qutb Shah strengthened the fort during the Mughal Prince Muhammad Azam's siege. Musa Khan Burj was built at the fort by Dharma Char, a Hindu architect, and Qutb Shahi General – Musa Khan Burj in the fort along with Qutb Shahi General – Musa Khan.

Along the wall, the Qutb Shahi Sultans built 87 bastions, some of which are octagonal and have battlement parapets on top. The bastions, known locally as Burj's, reinforce the outer wall at regular and short intervals all around its circle. Intima Burj, Bola Burj, Badhe Raksha Burj, Atishi Burj, Sample Burj, Nizam Burj, Husaini Burj, Masha Burj, Kaghzi Burj, Musa Burj, Paikar Burj, Washi Burj, Mastan Burj, Zafar Burj, Fauladi Burj, Kokha Burj, Saf-Shikan Burj are some of the noteworthy bastions Hira Burj, Firozi Burj, Madina Burj, Athara Sidhi Burj, Malik Shahi Burj, Dhaba Burj, Qutb Burj, Masjid Burj, Kalna Masjid Burj, Khuni Burj, Nagan Burj, Petla Burj, Azdah Burj, Ibrahim Burj, Pochamma Burj, Mahbub Burj, Mahbub Burj, Tawakkal.

The Sultans built eight gates around the fort. Fatah Darwaza, Bahamani Darwaza, Mecca Darwaza, Bodli Darwaza, Patancheru Darwaza, Banjara Darwaza, Jamali Darwaza, and Moti Darwaza are all 15 to 18 metres high. The gates are large and lofty, with sinuous approaches, outer and inner entrances, and enough recesses for the guards to stay between them. In India's history, Fatah Darwaza is one of the most important Darwaza. The Mughal armies entered the fort through this Darwaza, according to legend. Aurangzeb had bestowed the title. The principal architect of the Qutb Shahi dynasty was Dharma Char.

The Qutb Shahi Sultans built a temple for Hindu ministers and army officers in the fort. Madonna temple is the name of the sanctuary. It exemplifies Qutb Shahi's tolerance to the fullest. The Bala Hisar and the Baradari are major structures in the Golconda fort. Various symbols can be seen etched on the fort's walls and gates. There are figures of dogs, elephants, horses, fish, peacocks, sparrows, and flowers in the relevant architecture. Ashlars, bricks, and mortar were used to construct the structure. The construction of Golconda and other structures in Hyderabad used lime masonry with a thick covering of fine plaster. The Sultans possessed some of the best engineers in the world. They delivered water to Bala Hisar and Baradari in the fort without charging them. modern machinery and technology – supplied water from the lower section to the upper section of the fort. In one of the corners of Baradari, there is a secret subterranean passage that goes to Gosha Mahal, a distance of around 4-5 miles, which the Qutb Shahis used on the junctures of emergency and danger.

Major attractions:

The acoustics arrangement of the. The incredible Bollywood entertainer, Amitabh Bachchan loaned his voice to the shows held here. The show which incorporates sound and enhanced visualizations can be watched in English, Hindi and Telugu dialects. The fortification makes it remarkable. The sounds of

the claps at the fort's entrance may be heard plainly from the top of the hill. There are two rock-built pavilions outside the fort, Taramathi Gana Mandir and Premamathi Nritya Mandir, where the famous sisters Taramathi and Premamathi lived. The two sisters are reported to have performed on a circular dais at the top of the Kala Mandir edifice. This could be seen from the king's court from the top of the fort. Another feature is a light and sound display that attracts a large crowd

Significance:

A country's art and architecture are its cultural identity concerning other countries, so a country with great art and architecture is always prestigious to other countries. India's architecture is influenced by its history, culture, and religion. The opposing Hindu temple architecture and Indo Islamic architecture are the most well-known historical styles among various architectural styles and traditions. Both of them, especially the former, contain a variety of regional styles. After the Mughal Empire fell apart, regional nawabs in cities like Lucknow, Hyderabad, and Mysore continued to commission and promote the development of Mughal-style architecture in princely territories. Significance: A nation's art and architecture represent the country's cultural character to other countries, which is why a country with great art and architecture is always regarded as distinguished by other nations. India's architecture is influenced by its history, culture, and religion. The contrast between Hindu temple buildings and Indo Islamic architecture is the most well-known historical style among various architectural styles and traditions. Both of them, especially the former, contain a variety of regional styles. After the Mughal Empire fell apart, regional nawabs in places like Lucknow, Hyderabad, and Mysore continued to commission and promote the development of Mughal-style architecture in princely territories.

The fort:

The authority "Roundup of Monuments" ready by the Archeological Survey of India under the "Antiquated Monuments and Archeological Sites and Remains Act" records the Golconda Fort (seen in figure 1) as an archaeological fortune. Inside, there are numerous illustrious rooms and corridors, sanctuaries, mosques, magazines, corrals, and different designs, as well as a 10 km long external divider with 87 semi-roundabout strongholds (some actually equipped with cannons), eight passages, and four drawbridges. The most reduced of these is the peripheral fenced-in area, which we enter by the "Fateh Darwaja" (Victory Gate, so named on the grounds that Aurangzeb's victorious armed force walked in through this entryway) on the southeastern corner, which is studded with goliath iron spikes (to keep elephants from slamming it down). Fateh Drazan has a sound impact suggestive of Golconda's designing wonders. Hand applause at the entry's arch resounds and can be heard at the 'Bala Hisar' structure, the most noteworthy point just about a kilometre away. In case of an assault, this is filled in as an advance notice note to the Royals. Post Golconda is known for its mysterious acoustic framework.

The most elevated place of the fortification is the "Bala Hissar", which is found a kilometre away. There are castles, processing plants, a water supply framework, and the celebrated

"Rahman" cannon inside the post, in addition to other things. It is believed that a mystery burrow runs from the "Durbar Hall" to one of the royal residences at the lower part of the slope. The burial chambers of the Qutub Shahi rulers can likewise be found in the fortress. These graves, which display Islamic development, are about 1 kilometre north of Golconda's external divider. Delightful nurseries encompass them, as well as different masterfully cut stones.

There was additionally talk that Charminar had a mystery burrow. The fort is also home to the "Kala Mandir." It can be seen from the top of the Golconda from the king's durbar (king's court). This magnificent construction features lovely palaces and a clever water supply system. Regrettably, the fort's unusual construction is beginning to lose its allure. The fort's ventilation is incredibly stunning, with unusual designs. They were so well-crafted that a cool wind could reach the fort's inside, relieving the summer heat. The fort's massive gates are adorned with enormous sharp iron spikes. Elephants could not damage the fort because of the spikes. An outer wall of 11 kilometres (6.8 miles) encircles the fort of Golconda. This was constructed to strengthen the fort.

History:

The Kakatiya erected Golconda Fort along the lines of the KondaPalli Fort as part of their western defences. The city and castle were built on a 120-meter-high (390-foot-high) granite hill with enormous battlements. Rani Rudrama Devi and her successor Pratapa Rudra renovated and reinforced the fort. Later, the Kamma Nayakas took control of the fort after defeating the Tughlaq army occupying Warangal. It was given to the Bahmani Sultanate by Kamma monarch Musunuri Kapaya Nayaka in 1364 as part of a contract. Golconda gradually became obvious under the Bahmani Sultanate. Around 1501 Sultan Quli Qutb-ul-Mulk (r. 1487-1543), a Bahmani lead agent dispatched to Golconda, established the city as the seat of his administration. During this time, Bahmani rule declined, and Sultan Quli proclaimed freedom in 1538, establishing the Golconda-based Qutb shahi tradition. The initial three Qutb Shahi rulers formed the mud post into the ongoing building, a huge rock fortification arriving at approximately 5 kilometres all around, more than 62 years. The capital of the Qutb Shahi administration existed here until 1590 when it was moved to Hyderabad. The fortification was stretched out by the Qutb Shahis, who fabricated a 7-kilometre-long external divider that encompassed the city. Following an eight-month attack on account of Mughal head Aurangzeb, the fortification, at last, fell into decay in 1687.

Gates:

Golconda Fort features eight gates, the most important of which is Fateh Darwaja, or Victory Gate. The triumphant march of Mughal Emperor Aurangzeb was commemorated with the construction of this gate. Steel spikes deter elephants on the fence. The gate measures 25 feet long and 13 feet wide. The Nawabi style was used to construct the Balthasar Darwaja. The gate is gorgeous, and it was used to warn the fort's people about the danger. This was accomplished by clapping, which could be heard from the fort's highest point. On the 2" sides of the door are sculptures of legendary animals and lions. Sightseers are

simply permitted to enter the post through the Eastern Gate. It is the fortress' biggest entry.

The Bala Hisar Gate:

Balthasar (seen in figure 2) is a structure that has been visited by many 'Khas' and 'Aam'. But, most crucially, this structure was known for its acoustic properties. The Bala Hisar gate was designed so that a clap under the arch could be heard from the tallest point of the lavish pavilion. This system was used to send messages and listen in on conversations. The Curtain Wall encircled the Bala Hisar gate on the other side of the main entrance, preventing any attacker from gaining enough distance to breach it. In the event that you looked carefully, you can see openings in the door's curve. These were utilized to splatter aggressors with a liquid metal or hot oil. Bala Hisar entryway was studded with iron spikes that got elephants far from the stronghold, making it the zenith of the guard.

The treason at Fateh Darwaja:

The Mughal Sultanate was drawn to Golconda because of its wealth. The Mughal Emperor Aurangzeb aspired to conquer the remainder of Hindustan by invading the diamond state of Golconda because of its wealth and strategically excellent geographical location. However, the Mughal army was unable to penetrate the Golconda defence despite an eight-month siege. Golconda was impossible to defeat because of its fortified fortifications, war-efficient engineering, and spikes on the gate. Treason was required to bring Golconda down. Abdullah Khan Panni, a renegade, opened the fort's eastern gate for the Mughal forces. Aurangzeb eventually renamed the gate 'Fateh' (Victory) Darwaja. After conquering Golconda, Aurangzeb gained complete control of the Kullar diamond mines and became the world's wealthiest ruler of his day.

The Colossal:

The massive structure, which stands around 400 feet above the surrounding area and is 10 kilometres in circumference, comprises four district forts. There are 87 semicircular bastions on the outer wall that rise between 50 and 60 feet. To add to its colossal size, the fort features eight gates, which gave Aurangzeb's army's elephants a rough time for eight months. There is a parade ground, a palace, mosques, and temples of various establishments within the fortifications. But these aren't the only features that distinguish this, now-destroyed, human-made masterpiece. (As seen in figure 3)

The minarets of Golconda fort:

Three of the 87 bastions have historical significance in the fort's history. The fort's north-western minaret, Petal Burj is home to a magnificent 16-foot-long cannon known as Father Raihbir, which originally commemorated Alamgir's victory. The cannon extols the fort's colossal size. The Mosa Burj, a bastion in the south, is the next stop. Azahar Patkar stands on its land, an identical duplicate of the great Fath Ranbir. The Majnu Burj is the last bastion with the Alamgir Majnu cannon. (As shown in figure 4).

The storage at Golconda:

A massive infrastructure necessitated complimentary storage. The fort does have some enormous Kucha, which is amusing. Katora Houz, a massive cistern, was utilized to hold a great amount of water, where the monarchs would enjoy

boating in it. The palace also had a clever water system that used gravity to maintain a constant water flow to all portions of the fort. There is also a specific rainwater gathering system that provides water for agriculture and other purposes. The oil storage building, carved out of a single stone, is another storage option. At the time, it could store up to 12,000 gallons of oil at a time.

The carvings:

Each crevice, niche, and corner and the walls and gates have a story to tell. It was not simply a vault for some valuable gems, but also a coffin of stories told through carvings. Bala Hissar Gate, the fort's main entrance, is located on the citadel's eastern flank. Mythical beast statues guard it. It is constructed with a pointed arch decorated with peacock designs and scrollwork. Though the Mughal empire was the last to live there, several carvings still echo Hindu architecture, indicating its Hindu heritage. (As shown in figure 5).

Mosque:

Ibrahim Quli Qutb Shah Mosque was established by Quli Qutb Shah's son, Ibrahim. Staircases are leading to the Mosque after passing through the main gate. The Mosque is now damaged, but two minarets and three entrances close can still be found.

Taramati Mosque:

Taramati erected it in 1518 under Ibrahim Qutb Shah's rule. On each of the mosque's four corners, there is a minaret. The Mosque's courtyard is enormous and extends to the ramparts. (as seen in Figure 6).

Naya Qila (New Fort):

Naya Qila is a development of Golconda Fort, which was changed over into the Hyderabad Golf Club in the midst of resistance from nearby ranchers and NGOs. After the private area with a few pinnacles and the Hatiyanka Jihad "Elephant-sized tree" - an old baobab tree with an extraordinary circumference new fort's ramparts begin. There's also a war mosque there. Because of the Golf Course, public access to these locations is limited.

Qutub Shahi Tombs:

The tombs of the Qutb Shahi Sultans were located near the Golconda Fort. It's still referred to as seven tombs. Sultan Quli, Jamshid Quli, Ibrahim Quli, Muhammad Quli, Muhammad Qutb Shah, Abdullah Qutb Shah, and Abul Hassan Tanisha are all Qutb Shahi Sultans who played significant roles in Golconda's history. They ruled methodically and promoted Deccan traditions and culture. Their tombs are embellished with art and ornamentation. Following that, the Sultan Quli mausoleum - the dome is positioned on a raised square terrace - 100 feet each way. It is octagonal in structure, with the inner height of the hall being 30 feet 10 inches in each direction. A circular dome tops it, and from the outside, it looks to be a square structure due to the terrace. The basement storey's walls stand at a height of 20 feet.

His monument is very black basalt, with inscriptions carved in three bands in Naskh style and a beautiful Tauqi script³³. Jamshid Qutb Shah's second son, Sultan Quli, died of cancer in 1550 A.D. His grave is next to Sultan Quli. It is constructed straightforwardly. Nonetheless, it is a good dome with large

entrances and a well-decorated interior. In 1580 A.D., Ibrahim Qutb Shah died. Microwave is much more significant than Sultan Quli. It is adorned with Persian enamelled tiles, some of which may still be seen on the southern wall. The dome rises on a square terrace 117 feet long on each side. Two burials inside the dome, crown black basalt tombs on the exterior deck, all inscribed. It was recognised as one of Qutb Shahi emperors' most exquisite graves. In 1612 A.D., Muhammad Quli Qutb Shah died. His grave is lavishly ornamented, with beautiful art created using tiles. His enormous dome with an expansive double deck among the graves is unrivalled. The terrace stands at a height of 6 inches. The upper terrace measures 200 feet in each direction, while the lower terrace measures 126 feet and 3 inches. The dome's exterior dimensions are 71 feet and 3 inches in each direction, and colonnades are 22 feet tall. There are two entrance doors on the dome's south crown and eastern sides. In 1626 A.D.³⁴, Sultan Muhammad Qutb Shah died. His mausoleum has a square hall that measures 63.4" in each direction and an arcade that measures 19.8". The dome's facade is covered with enamelled tiles, which are still visible. It is also one of the Qutb Shahi tombs' largest tombs. In 1672 A.D.³⁵, Sultan Abdullah Qutb Shah died. His mausoleum is encircled on all sides by seven arches and has a platform that is 237 feet in length. It's a lovely dome with tiles all over it. It draws a considerable number of visitors. In 1699 A.D., Abul Hassan Tanisha died at Chini Mahal in Daulat Abad fort. He was a laid to rest in the graveyard of Syed Muhammad Gesudaraz Hussaini's father, Hazrat Syed Shah Raju Qatar. In Hyderabad, these Qutb Shahi tombs reflected Islamic and, in particular, Qutb Shahi style construction. (As seen in figure 7).

Sri Jagdamba Mahakali Temple:

It is situated on the fort's highest point. The temple is thought to have been built around 900 years ago. B The temple was constructed between the Ibrahim Mosque and the Emperor's residence Despite its tiny size, the temple attracts many devotees who come to pray. The Bonalu festival is particularly well-known in this region. It is thought that there existed a tunnel beneath the temple that could be used to flee to Charminar in the event of an attack or invasion. (as seen in Figure 8).

Rama Temple:

was constructed within the confines of the prison. According to folklore, Abul Hasan imprisoned Ramdas because he misappropriated the treasury. He drew images of Rama, Lakshman, and Hanuman in jail. A fair is conducted in the month of Ashada at the Yellamma Devi Temple, which was built at the peak.

Palaces:

The fort contains the ruins of imperial palaces. The emperors and their wives had royal mansions erected for them. Many more palaces have now been destroyed, with only a few pieces of them remaining.

The Sound and Light Show:

A music and light display that brings the mythology of Golconda to life is a new attraction at the fort. The story of Golconda unfolds across centuries of glory, with a magnificent mix of audio and visual elements. The play brings the glorious

past to life, and it is an enjoyable experience. The show is available in English, Hindi, and Telugu.

UNESCO World Heritage:

In 2010, the Permanent Delegation of India to UNESCO submitted the Golconda Fort and other QutbShahi dynasty monuments of Hyderabad, (the Charminar and the QutbShahi Tombs) for nomination as World Heritage Sites. They are currently on India's "provisional list."

Indo - Islamic architecture:

The fortress city of Golconda, located on the banks of the Musi River and rich in culture, prosperity, heritage, and architecture, was founded by Muhammad Quli Qutub Shah at the end of the 15th century and has since achieved a notable place in the history of Islamic heritage cities. In 1666, the Mughal Emperor Aurangzeb seized Golconda, and the city was razed to the ground. Finally, it was ruled by the great Nizams, who successfully restored Golconda's greatness. Golconda Fort, Charminar, Mecca Masjid, Paigah Tombs, Chowmahalla Palace, Mozamjahi Market and Taramati Baradari, and other heritage monuments have been inherited in Hyderabad. Golconda Fort is the most famous of them all. Golconda Fort is a pride of Hyderabad and one of India's most significant examples of fortifications. The location selection is made carefully to attain this goal. Mangalavaram Setting The hill and its location gave the Qutub-Shahi kings an advantage in establishing the formidable Qutub-Shahi empire. Golconda kingdom. This fort has operated as a solid administrative and military base for decades. Seven Qutub-Shahi rulers had their residence here. Golconda is the sole reason for this. The Qutb-Shahi kingdom has regained its renown and reclaimed its place in the history of Indo-Islamic ancestry.

5. Golconda as a Trade Centre during the Period of Qutub Shahis

There can be no sound state economy globally without industry, trade, and commerce. As a result, studying an enterprise is required to comprehend the economy. The kingdom of Golconda was known not just for its fertile grounds but also for its rich mines and other urban and rural enterprises. Several innovations in the Golconda kingdom contributed to steady growth in total economic activity during the 16th and 17th centuries. Simultaneously, successive Golconda kings and their minions devised adaptable techniques to exploit any source of wealth that caught their interest. As a result of these advancements, a succession of discoveries occurred in the early 16th century, leading to Golconda's emergence as one of the world's most important markets in the 17th century. The key industries that thrived in the Golconda empire are listed below.

Textile Industry:

Textiles have traditionally been a significant part of the Indian economy, coming in second only to agriculture in terms of output. The weavers made commodities in two types: piece goods and readymade. Plain cotton cloth, bleached, unbleached, or coloured red or blue, was marketed as clothing piece goods. Muslin or calico were the fabrics of choice. Calicoes were sturdy cloth that came in a variety of quality based on the fineness of the yarn and the number of threads per square inch;

they were in high demand both inside and outside the region. Readymade calico or muslin goods were tailored to meet the needs of international markets.

During this time, weaving centres were located in Kammappalli, Mattewada (Warangal), Bhimavaram, Achanta, Nagulapadu, Mellacheruvu, Kokkerini, Burrugugadda, Canada, Dharmavaram, Kopparam, Amritaluru, Alampur, Adoni, Velpumadugu, Proddatur, Paddukara, Animal, Hemavati, Lepak Furthermore, coastal towns such as Narsapur, Guntur, Pulicat, Bheemlipatnam, Masulipatnam, and others had a large weaving culture. They were making textiles at the time. Maggapu, gante, gutamu, paggamu pante, to kudu pante, palaka, done, parisariyachulu, cheedu dabbalu, dande, krovi koti pullalu, kudtari koyyalu, chopa yachalu, kota churru katti, karapu padugulu, golemu, Textile manufacturers in Telugu country included Pattusale, Devanga, Togata, Sale, Padmasale, Jandra, Mala, Wailuku, Moore's, and others. Parias also worked as a weaver, which allowed them to meet the requirements of their community. Weavers continued to weave many types and varieties of cloth, and they continued to sell their wares in their respective communities or at in-country fairs. This enormous number of small fairs known as Santas is mentioned in the Amuktamalyada. All of the community's family members were active in the manufacturing process at home. Female members were primarily responsible for the manufacturing of thread on the charkhas. The male members were mainly responsible for loom weaving and other processing tasks such as bleaching, printing, and painting. In one of his verses, the poet Srinatha notes that a housewife's responsibility was to labour on the spinning wheel.

European commerce businesses first appeared on the Golconda SeaBoard in the early 17th century. Settlements were founded by the Portuguese, Dutch, English, and French. They were too connected in the spice trade of the Malay Archipelago during the first part of the 17th century, for which Indian textiles were the staple commodity of barter. In truth, the exchange was three-sided. Bullion-laden ships sailed from Europe. The bullion was exchanged for a cotton piece in India, and goods were swapped for spices, which were shipped back to Europe. The Indian piece goods were primarily cotton, with one-third plain-woven material and two-thirds painted cloth. At the end of the 15th century the great Portuguese landed on the western coast of India, quickly displacing the Mohammedan traders who had been carrying on the spice trade even earlier. As a result, when the English and Dutch companies offered those Qalamkaris from the Madras regions, it was almost transparent that the Andhra Kalamkari were known to the inhabitants of spice land.

The kalamkari is a name given to a plain cloth that has been beautifully printed. This variation was a one-of-a-kind art form at the time, and it was only found in Golconda. The brush was used to create all colours and designs; their colour and arrangements were so permanent that they did not lose their lustre even after washing and lasted until the end. Masulipatnam chintz Kalamkari is a cloth designed using dye rather than a loom. The name kalamkari came into usage due to the employment of the qalam (or pen) in painting the designs.

The Persian word Qalam was adopted as a quill in Urdu during the Qutb Shahi period when commercial relations with Persia were solid. "The painting of this coast of Coromandel is famous throughout India and are indeed the most exquisite that are seen, the best wrought all with pencil and with such durable colours that notwithstanding they are often washed, the colours fade not while the cloth lasted, and this happens principally by a plant which growth in this country (Golconda), called by them chai," wrote William Method, a senior factor at Masulipatnam between A.D. 1618 The Qutb Shahi kingdom of Golconda had close ties to the Safavid court in Isfahan, Persia, at the time. Between A.D. 1603 and A.D. 1609, the Qutb Shahi capital had a hundred Persian embassies. It's no surprise, then, that by the early 17th century, the Safavid court in Persia was also a significant supporter of Golconda qalamkaris. Petapoli supplied painted fabric "used by the ruler of Golconda and the king of Persia for their soldiers," according to Dutch archives from 1607. Other evidence suggests that Persian horses, which were in high demand in Golconda, were traded for coloured cloth used in Persia as a lining for jackets and a bed and floor spread.

Diamond industry:

Between AD 1300 and 1600, the mining industry was a significant sector in India, mainly Andhradesa. Various mines operated in Andhradesa from the 14th to the 17th centuries under Vijayanagara and Qutb Shahi authority. The diamond mines played a significant part in the war. Andhradesa. The monarchs of Qutb Shahi and Vijayanagara supported mining and provided resources. Royalties to mining for digging up metal in different parts of Andhra Pradesh.

Diamond mining industry:

During medieval Andhra's Vijayanagara and Qutb Shahi periods, diamond mining, diamond cutting, and diamond set developed as a significant industry. Diamond is a tainted version of adamant. The term "naturally crystallised, pure carbon piece of substance" refers to a bit of carbon that has been naturally crystallised. Because it is the hardest substance known, it is essential to industry because it is used in rock drills and other instruments. as endorsing powder. As cutting glass This stone is recognised as a precious gem if it is clear and flawless. A gemstone with a high refractive power is utilised as a decorative item, significantly once it has been cut and polished. Especially for engagement rings, there is jewellery. The majority of visitors to Vijayanagara and Golconda agreed that massive worldwide renowned diamond mines were located in the three regions of the Vijayanagara and Golconda kingdoms, namely Karnataka on the banks of the Krishna and Golconda kingdoms on the banks of rivers Krishna and Golconda kingdoms on the banks of rivers Krishna and Golconda kingdoms on the banks of rivers Krishna and Golconda kingdoms on the banks of Rayalaseema, Godavari, and some portions of Godavari. Within fifteen days after arriving in Vijayanagara, Niccolò-de-Conti mentioned the existence of a diamond mine at Albenigaro, north of the capital. Ferando Nuniz said a diamond mine was in operation at the time. Gooty. Francisco Pereira, the king of Portugal's senior lapidary, dated his manuscript The year 1548 provides a detailed account of the many diamond mines in the

Vijayanagara Empire.

This is a list of Francisco Pereira's Vijayanagara diamond mines including Radique, Cortina, Ballary, and others. Carol, Condepelym, and Pempay are three characters. They were all in the northwestern part of the country. Vijayanagara's capital city. When it came to the diamond, it was stated to be "as big as a hen's egg." Vijayanagara's sack was discovered and delivered to Adil Shah. According to Conti, Raya had a jewel fastened to the base of the plume on his horse's headgear. Garcia Orta, who was in India in 1534, claims to have seen a Vijayanagara diamond the size of a hen's egg. He even claims that the weights of three others were 120, 148, and 250 pounds, respectively. mongrelised, with carat weights of 150, 175. Jacques-de-story coutre is told in another way. detailed information on the diamond mines under Vijayanagara's control Araviti Venkata-II ruled between 1611 and 1614 AD. The previous traveller described the energetic traveller. Ramallakota and Peli diamond mines are located in the eastern and southern directions of the country, respectively. Vijayanagara is a city in India.

According to Niccol de ' Conti, diamonds were discovered in the Kondaveeti dynasty's coastal region, who toured southern India, namely Vijayanagara empire. 'The primary mines were on the north bank of the Krishna River and in Kurnool and Anantapur,' he adds. Not just in Vajarakarur, but also other countries. Based on the preceding information, it is possible to conclude that no in the western direction of Vijayanagara, there was a diamond mine. As a result, the preceding Anantapur, Kurnool, Cudahy, and Anantapur, Kurnool, Cuddapah, and Anantapur, Kurnool, Cuddapah, and Anantapur, Kurnool, Cuddapah Andhradesa's Guntur. The foreign accounts also reveal details regarding the government's approach toward diamond mines. According to Portuguese accounts, the diamond mine at Vajarakarur was considered a state monopoly, with the Vijayanagara Emperor as the owner.

Proprietor. Similarly, the Emperor held the diamond mines of Ramallakota, according to the Spanish document of Jacques-de-Coutre. During the Middle Ages, rulers also entrusted the management of the mines to a group of capable and loyal officers. They also gave contractors the rights to mines on occasion. The Vijayanagara dynasty founded the Vijayanagara Empire. The system, as mentioned earlier, was in use at the time of the monarchs. The renters used to make a yearly payment to the landlord emperor. During the Qutb Shahi dynasty, Andhradesa remained a major diamond mining and trading centre.

Contemporary European travel diaries under the Qutb Shahis of Iran include vital information regarding diamond mines, diamond trading, diamond cutting, and polishing activity. Golconda. Diamond mining is also discussed in native literature and Telugu Kaifiyats. under the rule of the Qutb Shahis in the Golconda empire, and the mining sector was immensely profitable. Andhradesa's in the Middle Ages. By the 17th century, the Golconda diamonds had become so well-known that the word Golconda symbolised opulent wealth in European countries. According to the Oxford dictionary, "Golconda" is used synonymously with "Mine of Wealth,". Previously known for its gems. Since time immemorial, the allure of diamonds has

lured ambitious adventurers to the Coromandel Coast from far-flung lands such as ancient Rome and Phoenicia, Arabia, China, Venice, France, and England. According to a report published in England in 1677, Golconda territory contained 23 diamond mines. Although some of these locations remain a mystery to researchers, the majority of these mines are currently found in California.

Andhra Pradesh is a state in India. Geologists divided these mines into two categories: those in the north and those in the south. Districts of Cuddapah, Kurnool, Anantapur, and Guntur, Krishna, and West Godavari districts. According to Thevenot, a French traveller, the kingdom of Golconda was known as the Diamond Kingdom. Tavernier, another explorer, claimed that the Golconda kingdom had twenty-three internationally renowned other diamond mines. Until recently, all diamond mines existed. The Qutb Shahis was defeated. Because of the ambiguity of some of these mines, they were not identified. Information on the location of mines provided by European travellers. The majority of the mines were also alive during the Vijayanagara period. The Golconda diamond mines were well-known throughout India. The era of Vijayanagara Golconda mines thrived throughout the Vijayanagara Empire, which lasted until the 16th century. Despite its fall in 1564, it is virtually completely intact. Ibrahim Qutb Shah brought the Kondapalli and Konadu Circles under the strong rule of Golconda a year before his death in 1579. Golconda took control of the diamond mines along the coast of Andhra Pradesh. Mining continued from then on. Merchants and the Dutch, to whom the mines were leased out, on a smaller scale condition that all diamonds weighing more than 10 carats be surrendered to the King. When Mohammed Qutb Shah came to power, diamond mining in the coastal area became a state monopoly. Until 1623, he was particularly interested in this. The Rayalaseema diamond mines, however, remained. Bijapur and the Vijayanagara emperors ruled these lands until 1652 when Bijapur and the Vijayanagara monarchs invaded them.

The Mughal Emperor gave his consent to Golconda. Mirjumla cultivated the mines near Gandikota, while the King was granted access to the most famous mine at Vajrakarur in Guntur taluk. Athanasius Nikitin, a Russian adventurer, visited the last-mentioned mine in 1472. He had 300 people assigned to him. There were diamond traders residing in this location, and diamonds were exported from here to all parts of the world. Indeed, these mines never stopped supplying diamonds to the world. The Vijayanagara emperors' Vajrabhandagra (diamond treasury). Countless foreign tourists, including Abdur Razzak, Varthema Panento, Nuniz, Domingo Paes, Niccolo de Conti, and Duarte Barbosa, praised the splendour of the vanished kingdom. Linschoten noted in 1585 that diamonds larger than 25 mongrelise were found at the Vajrakarur mine. The Vijayanagara king is the only one who has access to it. Barnades claims that in 1614, at the treasury at Three big chestfuls of finest diamonds were found in Chandragiri, the Vijayanagara capital.

This is the result of everything. Shows that the Golconda diamond mines on Krishna and Pennar are the same as Golconda. Diamond mines in Vijayanagara. As a result, these

mines are known as Golconda Diamond Mines. During the latter 50 to 60 years of Qutb Shahi's rule, he became internationally famous. The most prominent mine in Andhradesa is Kollur, which is now in the Guntur district and was once located on the bank of the Krishna River. Tavernier saw this mine when it was a major town with the mines in the shape of a cross between the town and high mountains. "Which were about a league and a half away" from the town. This mine produced well-known products. Diamonds in India, and it produced many stones ranging in size from 10 to 900 carats, with some stones exceeding 900 carats a much bigger. Varadkar in Bellary district, now in Anantapur district, was another notable diamond mine. This diamond mine employed about 40,000 men. In the Varadkar mine, the Orloff diamond was discovered. Even before the Qutb shahi era, this mine was active.

Vest claims that For the Qutb Shahis, this was the most important mine. Every day, almost 6000 people toiled in this mine. About 3-pound diamonds were extracted." Malleable and Gollapally were the other major mines in the Krishna and Godavari districts. The Mallappally and Gollapally diamond mines employed between 30,000 and 40,000 people, according to Streynsham Master. During his voyage to Golconda, Streynsham Master paid a visit to the kingdom. Mallepally and Gollapally diamond mines were awarded to Abul Hasan Tanishah during his period. On a year-to-year lease for 60,000 pagodas (2,40,000 rupees). The Paritala diamond mine, located in the Krishna district of India, was another large diamond mine. Andhradesa, home of the world-famous diamond.

Approximately 6000 to 7000 people were employed as the mine labourers. Rajipenta's diamond mine was set in a lovely green valley. The lush green meadows encircled this location stretched far and wide, blending into the distant heavenly blue horizon. The ten-mile stretch between Rajipenta and Mustabad was breathtakingly beautiful. Government Rajipenta provided an annual revenue of 60,000 various. Thousands of Rajipentas were made. During the Qutb Shahi dynasty, magnificent gems were found. Small diamonds were mined at the Gandikota mine. It is a part of the state of Karnataka. 1200 labourers were employed in this mine to dig diamonds. The larger diamonds were sent to the monarchs of Qutb, while the smaller stones were transferred to other countries. The employees had honed their skills to the point that they could identify diamonds simply by looking at the mound's nature, scent, and colour. New mines and diamonds were discovered when Mohammad Sayeed, the Mirjumla, captured Cuddapah, Siddawot, and Gandikota. Millions of rupees were discovered. The supply of diamonds was so great that they couldn't keep up with demand.

Bags, not numbers, we're used to counting the items. Sayeed had amassed a sizable diamond collection. He had gifted Shahjahan with a large diamond worth millions of rupees, which he had delivered to him, It was 360 carats in weight. All of these gems were found in Karnataka. It was no exaggeration to say that the Golconda kingdom produced most of the world's large diamonds. Both Abdullah Qutb Shah and his successor, Abul Hassan Qutb Shah, possessed knowledge. Their jewellery warehouse has numerous diamonds weighing at least 300

carats. Abdullah's crown was encrusted with the finest gems. Bills of exchange were accepted in place of ready currency in Agra, Golconda, Bijapur, and, preferably, Surat.

If a buyer could not pay right away, the interest of 112 per cent per mensem was levied. All merchants were required to produce a sales register to the province's governor. The mine that would be able to compute and collect the royalties for precisely weighing the diamonds at the mine, the king appointed men who conducted the job without charging anything. Tavernier was taken aback when he discovered that children "from the age of ten years up to fifteen" were involved. and sixteen" were educated in the skill of buying diamonds from mines and selling them off in the future.

In Andhra Pradesh, the diamond mining industry was not seasonal but ran all year, and diamonds were gathered in various ways, depending on the preferences of the travellers. Diamonds were taken from the beds of diamonds during the wet season. After the showers, there were torrential downpours. Diamonds were collected from the mountains and the sea in the summer. The extreme heat of the season made it difficult for guests to visit. Of them, the king was reported to own diamond mines in the kingdoms of Golconda and Vijayanagara. These areas were turned into protected towns.

Export of diamonds and diamond trade:

With the authority of the ruler of Calicut, Zamorin, Portuguese traders arrived in India in 1498 and founded trading centres in Calicut, Goa, Diu, Daman, and Malacca. They had cordial connections with the kings of Vijayanagara. The Portuguese, the Dutch, and the Belgians are all members of the European Union. Companies in England were persuaded to fulfil the needs of the European markets into which they had entered. when long-distance trade between India and Europe became more common Throughout the 16th and 17th centuries. They were crucial in trade and commerce. The diamond mining sector allowed them to broaden their purchasing options, including diamonds in Andhra Pradesh, pepper and spices in Malabar, and textiles in Kerala. Coromandel. It is clear from the European testimonies that the Europeans, namely Germans and French, were the ones who made the decision. Before the Qutb, Portuguese traders had diamond trading links with the Andhra region, and the Shahis ascended to the throne. The Muslim rulers of Deccan fostered diamond mining and trading after the battle of Tallikota.

The Golconda Sultan continued his hunt for new diamond mines, and the discovery of fresh mines at Coastaconda, Cuddapah, Duane Guti, Nueva, and Pali provided extra cash. kingdom. In the year 2000, the Kollur diamond mine in the kingdom of Golconda was discovered. As recorded by William Methwold in the 17th century, diamonds were recovered from Kollur. It has been one of Andhra Pradesh's most important mines for a long time. In the diamond mining sector, there are some noticeable variations in the policies implemented by the Vijayanagara rulers and the Muslim rulers of Deccan, and mining allotments and access to mining rights had been restricted. During the Vijayanagara period, foreigners were prohibited from entering, but the Qutb Shahis leased out mining rights. In the seventeenth century, the Dutch were granted

powers.

Furthermore, the Qutb Shahis had established a unique economic system. and political arrangements in which the diamond mines' yields were used following their value Apart from maintaining it under their possession, they have their requirements and due to circumstances. Later, the Muslim monarchs transferred the diamond mines to mine controllers, who appeared to be merchants who had formed a corporation. These merchant capitalists put up substantial sums of money and carried out mining activities. A government permit is required. As a result, the diamond mining industry evolved along commercial lines.

During the seventeenth century Whatever differences there may have been in the two countries' policy, all diamonds larger than a certain size were deemed illegal by the Vijayanagara monarchs and the Qutb Shahis. It was the royal property that had to be turned over to the king's treasury. With the collapse of the royal capital in A.D. 1565, the King of Portugal's official agreement to buy diamonds from the city of Vijayanagara ended. Several merchants whose names appear in later records demonstrate that they did business in the area of diamonds. As a result, private and foreign merchants left Goa and travelled to other locations to purchase diamonds, which they did in most cases directly from the mines. Bernardo de Nordona, a Venetian trader, was busy buying. During 1606 at Bijapur, he was buying diamonds and selling them at the Ramallakota market mine. Some private merchants from Portugal, such as Jorge de Silveria, have been discovered. In A.D. 1611, a document shows a man buying diamonds at the Ramallakota mine. Another is Vincent Ribeiro. Between 1616 and 1622 A.D., the Portuguese were buying diamonds in Bijapur.

Alvaro Mendez visited the Marmur mine and purchased fine diamonds from Portuguese private merchants, including Bartholome Rodriguez, Domingos de Port, and Alvaro de Fonseca, before departing from Santhome of Mylapore. He lived in Madras until 1684 when he became involved in the diamond trade. a few Germans Merchants like Felipe Escudo had moved to Goa with their wives and children. In A.D. 1620, he left the area and dwell in Sant home in Myla pore. He took a trip. He spent most of his time in South India's hinterland, buying and selling gems and other valuables stones of great value. The Dutch East India Company was drawn to the Andhradesa's diamonds. In AD 1621, authorities from the Dutch East India Company discovered a fresh diamond mine in Banaganapalli, about fifty miles south of Masulipatnam's harbour. It was rented out. for 30,000 pagodas each year by the Sultan of Golconda Diamonds weighing more than a tonne can be found at this mine.

Moreover, eight carats were discovered, which had to be handed to the Sultan of Oman free of charge Golconda. Muslims, Gujaratis, and other indigenous participated in the diamond trade under the Vijayanagara and Golconda Sultans' reigns. Traders from Europe, such as the Portuguese, Dutch, and English, arrived in India and built trading centres along the coast. Andhradesa has a thriving diamond industry. Andhradesa diamonds were traded to other countries. Masulipatnam, Petapoli, Pulicat, and Porto Nova are the ports you can travel to

Europe.

Masulipatnam Port is located in the state of Andhra Pradesh, India. During the Qutb Shahi dynasty, it played a significant role in diamond commerce. 19,000 carats of diamonds and 70,000 pagodas were sent from the Kollur mine to Goa and Surat, respectively (80,000 pagodas). There are 18,000 pagodas in Masulipatnam and 23,000 pagodas in Madras, with a similar number sold in other cities Golconda. The Andhradesa's diamonds, on the other hand, held a prominent position in commerce and also possessed a significant amount of value. Demand is high throughout the world. The diamond mines brought quite a lot of money to the Vijayanagara and Golconda states. They promoted the diamond sector, as well as diamond exports and imports. The monarchs owned some of the diamond mines, while others were leased. As a result, in Medieval times, the diamond mines in Andhradesa contributed significantly to the state's revenue, exports, and imports.

Iron industry:

Since the arrival of the Aryans, the Indian subcontinent has had a strong reputation in the art of manufacturing and using the iron. As part of it, the Andhradesa's region has been a well-known arm-producing centre for a long time. The kings and citizens of the state recognized the value of iron. As a result, every state promoted iron mining and military implements and agricultural fields, which are the most practical in everyday life. The Qutb Shahi monarchs of medieval Andhra were known for producing the highest-grade iron and steel in the world. This was confirmed by modern foreign travellers who stated that Golconda produced high-quality iron and steel in high demand both in India and overseas. The arrival of the Muslim troops in the Deccan dramatically changed the typology and quality of guns and armour in the Telugu region.

Arms and armaments used in battles, such as firearms (such as cannons), long double-edged swords with a pistol-shaped hilt, guns, spears, helmets, battle axes, guards, sheaths, pans, shields, cannonballs, blades, arm ornamentation, and so on, were made in the Kingdom. The Golconda monarchy was known for its armaments manufacturing and marketing. Many buyers flocked to Hyderabad to purchase weapons and other military equipment. Gadwal, Wanaparti, Kolapur, Nirmal, Lingampalli, Yelgandel, Warangal, Umrichinta, and Aurangabad were among the several arm manufacturing centers in the region. Bhonagiri, Velikonda, Kurnool, Kolluru, Cuddapah, Tirupati, Ramulkota, Ganjam, Nizampatnam, Pochampadu, Narsapur, Konapur, Mailavaram, Ananthagiri, Vijayanagaram, Jadevepur, and Srirangapatnam were among the other centers visited. During this time, manufacturing institutions known as "Kharkhans" were run by state and private individuals. The majority of the manufacturers were concentrated in the cities.

The Golconda rulers focused their efforts on assembling a large artillery force, both in terms of troops and material. Both small and large, forts, bastions, and embrasures were outfitted with a slew of guns and amassed massive ammunition stockpiles. In Andhra Desa, iron and bronze artillery pieces were cast in several locations. Thousands of men were enlisted in various divisions of the army. Arms, armour, and

ammunition were handed to them. The armaments industry employed a variety of metals. Bows and arrows, javelins, war clubs, swords and shields, daggers, battle-axes, coats of mail, helmets, armguards, knuckle guards, animal armour, horseshoes, nails, stirrups, all kinds of artillery pieces, matchlock guns, cannonballs of various sizes, and other equipment were all made of iron, bronze, and steel.

Curved swords with the forward edge talwar became increasingly popular, and Zuma, an Arabian hunting knife, was introduced. As the Central Asian, Turkish, and Persian prototypes, various new varieties of daggers, such as the peshkabja, jumbia, and khanjar, were also brought. However, the traditional Indian daggers jamadhara and katar continued to be used. Swords like the Khanda and Tega were equally popular among the Muslim nobility. 32 The barrels of Golconda soldiers' muskets were stronger than those of any European muskets, according to Jean-Baptist Tavernier, because they were made of finer steel, and this iron and steel were cheaper in Masulipatnam than in Japan; this is why the Indonesians imported the Golconda kingdom's iron and steel.

Coal industry:

Since ancient times, it has been in India as a complement to the iron and steel industries. The Kingdom had some coal mines, similar to Golconda. Coal was used to burn or smelt the iron needed to manufacture needed instruments, such as battle weapons, domestic utensils, and agricultural implements. The charcoal, which was available locally, was recorded by Antony Schorer. The Coromandel region is his definition (statement) of "locally." It is safe to assume that he worked as a factor/officer for the Dutch East India Company at Masulipatnam in the early 17th century, and Masulipatnam was Golconda's harbour town. Ireland, Wardha or Chanda, Singareni, and Godavari valleys are home to some of the most well-known mines.

Building construction industry:

The Qutb Shahis were master builders noted for their spectacular structures. The Sultans constructed a plethora of forts, buildings, mosques, and Ashur Khanas, among other things. They were well-known for their spectacular structures. During the Qutb Shahi Sultans reign, the building construction industry employed thousands of professional and unskilled laborers and masons around the Kingdom. Dar-us-Shifa, Golconda Fort, Hyderabad City, Charminar, Daria-e-Mir Momin (Necropolis), Four HighWays, Tombs Hayathnagar, Ashur Khanas, Masjids, Balagate, Mortuary, Fort Rissala, Navmahal, Nakorkhana Balahissar, Shilakhana, Amberkhana, Shamsheer Kota, Telkadhoka forts, Jabbarkota, Taramati and Premamati palaces, the hall of justice, Syedabad fort, Mirpet fort. The Qutb Shahi Sultans and their nobility contributed equally to the construction of Hindu temples during the period, as evidenced by contemporary records, demonstrating the Qutb Shahi Government's liberal policy toward its subjects.

As part of the state's religious tolerance policy, the Qutb Shahi government sponsored the construction and renovation of temples by allocating villages and lands for their upkeep. Knacherla Gopanna, also known as Ramdas, Taluqdar of Nelakondapally Pargana (Khammam Dist.) and nephew of Akkanna and Madonna, Abul Hasan Tana Shah's Ministers,

built the Sri Rama temple at Bhadrachalam in Khammam District in A.D. 1684. The Sultan contributed the villages of Bhadrachalam, Shankara Giri, and Palvancha to the temple's upkeep. He established a tradition of sending the Mutyala Talamburu on Sri Rama Navami, still practised today. Madonna, Tanashah's capable Prime Minister, coordinated the construction of many new temples and the renovation of ancient ones around the Kingdom. As a result, the Qutb Shahi Sultans, aristocracy, and higher officials in the State supplied everyday work for the state's labourers, skilled craftsmen, and masons, contributing to the development of building activities during their reign.

Sugar and jaggery industry:

During the Qutb Shahi dynasty in Andhradesa, sugar made from sugarcane was regarded as a significant consumption item. Sugarcane was planted extensively, and mills for extracting juice from it were also mentioned. This was used to make sugar and jaggery, which were widely used in domestic and temple ceremonies to prepare food sacrifices to Gods. Sugar and sugarcane were widely used in Andhra during the 16th and 17th centuries, evidenced by poets like Srinatha and Vemana. Sugar and jaggery are used in the *naivedya*, an important aspect of worship. Temple aided this industry by either acquiring it or entering into a contract to secure a steady supply. Panaka is located at the Panakala Narasimha Swamy temple in Mangalagiri, Guntur District. The gurgling sound of jaggery water being poured into the lord's mouth is almost audible as if the lord is sipping it. The temple was given this name as a result of this unique feature. Jaggery is consumed throughout the year. They were favourites of the sweet meats made of sugar or jaggery after establishing Muslim dominance in Andhradesa. They were so encouraged to cultivate sugar cane in the Kingdom. Sweets such as *seminarian*, *queer*, *jalebi*, *mitahkhana*, *sherbet*, and *matkiyan* (pots filled with sugar/jaggery and milk) were produced on special occasions.

Pottery Industry

Even though potters' services have been in high demand in society since the birth of civilization, allusions to them or their crafts are largely absent from medieval literary epigraphs. However, the lack of information about this vital industry in medieval literature does not diminish the importance of ceramics in medieval Andhra culture. However, references to the potter and his works may be found in a few stone epigraphs in classical Telugu literary works such as *Hamsavimsati*. Based on this data, it is possible to state that the pottery industry prospered in medieval Andhra. The potter's art evolved in different nations, at different times, and along different lines, but it always began as a handicraft utilizing clay found in riverbeds or tank beds. Over time, more and more aesthetic products were created and numerous sophisticated shapes. Colours were employed to embellish the clay vessels, and a clear glaze was occasionally poured to give them a nice sheen. There was also an attempt to make the commodities more aesthetic by painting and applying colour. Because the potter used the wheel to make the pots, he could produce them in vast quantities. In epigraphs from the Middle Ages, references to *Kummari Sari* and the imposition of a tax on the potter's wheel

and the profession of the potters demonstrate the existence of pottery as an industry. The potters, carpenters, artisans, shepherds, and others, were employed by the temples to provide necessary earthen vessels. Temple records also show that the potters were hired by the temples, who provided specified land plots and paid their salaries in cash. In this context, the inscription states that the potter must give the temple earthenware, referred to as *kaduvulu*. Another epigraph mentions the provision of five cinnamon and six *khadi* in the form of rice-growing land for the potter's head (*pedda kumari*). 65 Aside from these sporadic references, little is known about the potter or his early medieval works.

A bilingual inscription in Telugu and Persian dated A.D. 1620 revealed interesting facts. *Khairat Khan*, an officer of *Mohammed Quli Qutb Shah* at *Pangal* in *Mahabubnagar* district, issued this record. It mentions the erection of a watchtower called *Bala Kehilla* at the summit of the castle and a well in the fort's potter's street. This indicates that the potters lived on a separate street within the fort. However, the potter did not need to live in each community, according to the *Atthavana Vyavahara Tantram* acquired by *Mackenzie*. It would be adequate if one or two stayed in the hamlet and provided the ceramic ware required for that settlement.

Potters used to sell their ceramic vessels at marketplaces on occasion, depending on the demand they were paying the government *chakra kanika*. The large-scale preparation of ceramic vessels, both for villagers' needs and as commodities for sale in market towns/places, reveals the growth of potter's art as an important cottage industry throughout this period. Of seven exquisite words in *Hamsavimsati*, the potter and his craft are mentioned. This work's extensive description of materials, preparing pottery shapes, types of earthenware, and their decorating aids us in better understanding the services potters provide in society. The potter, referred to as *ghatikara chakravartin* in the poetic descriptions, brings clay just like the boar lifts the earth from the oceans, prepares the ceramics with great enthusiasm just like *Brahma* creates the Universe, turns the potter's wheel several times just like *Lord Vishnu* turns his *cakra*, bakes the sun-dried earthenware just like *Lord Siva* burns in the burial ground, prepares the potter vessels in large numbers and piles them. *Hamsavimsati* includes *kagu*, *majjiga*, *mum*, *Kadavu*, *guanabana*, *vesalabudiga*, *purapuchatti*, *mountain*, *Dutta*, *pidata*, *mukudu*, *binde*, *pramide*, *chevula penemu*, *golems*, *chillula sibbi*, *done Totti*, *gunmetal*, *dumapatra*, *sanike*, and other utensils made by modern the author carefully indicated the situations when certain pieces were used. Based on *Hamsavimsati*'s verse, one might determine the potter's financial situation. The potter's financial situation was healthy, and he lived contentedly without any debts. It also adds that he owns the gold jewellery and has a solid socioeconomic standing in society.

Salt industry:

Uppuleka Ruchi puttaganatayya Bhaskara, according to *Bhaskara Satakam*, indicates there is no flavour in meals without salt. The significance of salt was noted in medieval time poetry. Salt has been produced in the Deccan Coastal areas since prehistoric times. In ancient days, salt was also a royal

monopoly. "The superintendent of the ocean shall attend to the collecting of salt and supervise the commerce of this product," states Kautilya, the author of *Arthashastra*. Salt was frequently generated in medieval Andhradesa through the evaporation of seawater. Salt manufacturing and sale were controlled by the Qutb Shahi regime, with concessionaires designated by the state allowed to sell salt. This was produced in salt pans (upper *madis*) near the Golconda coast.

When Sultan Abdullah transferred the monopoly to private merchants, the price of salt skyrocketed, and it was sold "for the price of silver." Khadija Begum, King Abdullah's sister, was married to Ali Adil Shah – II, the king of Bijapur, and when she learned of the people's anguish, she wrote to her brother, requesting that the monopoly of the intermediaries be removed immediately, or "he would be held up on the day of Judgment." The Sultan revoked his orders after receiving this letter, bringing the price of salt back to normal. It informs us about the current public demand for salt. Coastal towns such as Masulipatnam, Pedda Ganjam, China Ganjam, Peddapalli, Bapatla, Nizamapatnam, and others had salt manufacturing centres. Uppupentas was used to store salt, while Vietnamese were used to measure it. According to the sources, the salt trade was dominated by Komatis and Banjars during this period.

6. Conclusion

The Development of the Golconda fort between the thirteenth and seventeenth centuries has been chronicled in this dissertation, which includes many details not found in survey books in the classic narrative of its growth. Possibly the first phase of development at Golconda, a city in India, yielded noteworthy findings. Scholars of the fort have long contested this period. Furthermore, the first foundation at Golconda was fairly big, according to this study. Two contiguous enclosures near the summit of the Bala Hisar citadel and a third enclosure appear to have been part of the fort's initial phase.

There are a variety of gates, bastions, and other features that can be added This occupation phase is related with. All subsequent extensions to Golconda were erected inside the footprint of this foundation throughout the next 150 years. When the Bahmanis (1347-1538) took control of Golconda in the mid-fourteenth century, the fort became a vital link in the trade network. Three additional features were built in the eastern boundary defences of this kingdom at the site. This time, a gate was added to the inner fort's eastern flank, as well as a mosque and a cemetery Within the second enclosure, a hall was constructed. The layout of Golconda did not change significantly until Sultan Quli's youngest son Ibrahim's reign (1550-80). It became a royal capital for the first time, as evidenced by the shape of its new outside walls and the size of its palace area, and its funerary zone designated as a dynasty necropolis with an official designation, the entrance is stunning. The later Qutb Shahi sultans (until 1687) made no additions, Ibrahim's boundaries have been determined.

First and foremost, the fort's construction reflects the region's militarization in the 1550. The Yadavas, Hoysalas, and Kakatiyas, who ruled the Deccan at the period, were Suddenly a new opponent from the north, Delhi's sultans eventually

ascended to the throne captured the region, but a slew of revolts erupted because they couldn't keep control of it. In place of the bigger dynasties, petty chieftains rose to prominence. Later, a different set of ideas determined the placement of architectural features on the site. The early to the mid-sixteenth-century form of Golconda was based on a model created in Delhi around 1320 and was duplicated in Golconda. Each of the sites was held by Muslim dynasties when they conquered and settled the Deccan is a region in India. In the Qutb Shahi palace area, rather than reacting to practical problems, Within the landscape, a congregational mosque, graves, and gates were placed for the effect is stunning. A wall separated the palace area from the rest of the town, a fence and a gate.

This Dissertation has also expanded our understanding of Indo-Islamic architecture, formerly a fairly narrow topic of study. Golconda, along with Firozabad and Bidar, is unique in this region for possessing such a well-preserved complex of palace buildings. The palace area at Golconda, on the other hand, had remained undeveloped until this point. Neither the wealth of its content nor its significance has been fully studied. Although the ornamental application of stucco and tiles began in Iran, it is unknown whether Iran was the direct source of these methods at Golconda. Both were employed in Bahmani architecture.

when they were initially introduced to the Deccan and the Deccan architecture of Sultanates who came after the Bahmani dynasty. Their arrival in Golconda could be explained as a series of events. Rather than as a continuation of a tradition that had become commonplace in the Deccan by that time, a new Iranian invention. The structural changes in Qutb Shahi architecture are also likely to explain ties to Iran. Between the time the fourteenth-century mosque on the Golconda citadel was built and the Golconda citadel was built, vaulting methods evolved. Sultan Quli built a congregational mosque in 1518, which he later remodeled during Ibrahim's reign (1550-80). It's only natural that Iran would be a source of inspiration for Deccan arts. Iran was seen as the country of the Qutb Shahis, the birthplace of Sultan Quli, and a source of fine culture. However, while Iran has long been recognized as a significant influence in Qutb Shahi art and architecture (particularly by Golconda painting specialists), this dissertation also highlights the significance of Telangana's local traditions in the arts of Qutb Shahi. This dynasty has existed for a long time; the sultans of Qutb Shahi were cognizant of their region's history, not only because of its aesthetic appeal but also because of its utility as a source of indications of life. The power of government During the reign of Frederick William III, architecture and movable artefacts were created. Ibrahim Qutb Shah, in particular, exemplifies the blending of many traditions to which the country is home Access was granted to Qutb Shahis. Images of hamzas and yales mixed with peacocks and lions in Qutb Shahi imagery. Acts carried out Repairs to public works in Kakatiya, for example provide further indication that this is the case, the link was cultivated on purpose.

This paper finally positioned Golconda in history by examining each of these aspects of the fort and its growth. It is now feasible to distinguish between different stages of

development, comprehend each sultan's contribution to the site, and place Golconda in a regional perspective. Above all, this work is important. provides new scholarly opportunities based on the premise that understanding the Deccan and Telangana's unique socio-political background is crucial. Understanding the architecture of this place and time is crucial.

Fig. 1. Golconda fort

Fig. 2. Bala Hissar gate

Fig. 3. The gigantic of Golconda fort

Fig. 4. The ruins of Golconda fort

Fig. 5. Carvings of the Bala Hissar gate

Fig. 6. Taramati mosque

Fig. 7. Qutub shahis tombs

Fig. 8. Shri Jagdambika temple

References

- [1] Science is derived from the latin word 'scientia' meaning knowledge enterprise that builds and organizes knowledge in the form of testable e and predictions about the world. The scientific revolution of the 16t centuries marked a new way of studying the natural world, by experimentation aimed at defining 'laws of nature*.
- [2] Irfan Habib, Technology in Medieval India, Tulika Books, Delhi, 20 p. ix.
- [3] Abul Fazl, Ain-i Akbari, vol. 1, Eng. tr. by H. Bloch Calcutta, 1873, p. 223.
- [4] Calcium oxide is commonly called Quick Lime. I plaster in the form of calcium hydroxide CaOH lime.
- [5] Abul Fazl, op. cit., p. 224.
- [6] Ibid., p. 222.
- [7] Saqi Musta'd Khan, Maasir-i Alamgiri, Eng. tr. by Jadunath Sarkar, The Asiatic Society, New Delhi, 2nd edn. 1986, p. 183.
- [8] See Mahomed Kasim Ferishta, Tarikh-i Ferishta, Eng. tr. by John Briggs, History of the Rise of the Mahomedan Power in India, vol. iii, Delhi, reprint 1981 (First Published 1829). Also see S.A. A. Bilgrami, Landmarks of the Deccan, New Delhi, reprint, 1992 (First Published in 1927).
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